

Effects of deep placement of urea by reflooding water.^a CNRRI experimental farm, Hangzhou, China, 1986.

Application method	Urea N applied (kg N/ha)				Grain yield (t/ha)	Brown rice protein (%)	N uptake (kg/ha)	Utilization (%) of applied urea N	N efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
	BT ^b	10 DT ^c	30 DT ^c	Total					
Control	0	0	0	0	6.6 c	6.74	93 c	0	71
Surface broadcast	0	56.25	56.25	112.5	7.2 b	7.66	129 b	32 d	55
Deepplaced by water	0	56.25	56.25	112.5	7.4 a	7.78	145 ab	46 b	51
Surface broadcast	67.5	33.75	33.75	135.0	7.4 a	7.62	148 ab	41 c	50
Deepplaced by water	28.3	56.25	28.20	112.5	7.4 a	7.74	149 a	50 a	50

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bBefore transplanting. ^cDays after transplanting.

Potassium nutrition of rice

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We studied K nutrition of rice in a pot experiment using poor-fertility loam soil: 0.56% organic matter, 0.045% N, 1.8% P, 61 ppm K, pH 8.3, and EC 0.6 mmho/cm. Treatments are in the table.

Twentyday-old Basmati 370 seedlings were used. Half were dipped in 0.7% K₂SO₄ solution and half in distilled water. Fertilizer was 100 kg N and 44 kg P/ha.

Dipping seedling roots in a 0.7% solution of K₂SO₄ for 72 h before

Effect of K application method on rice growth, yield, and K concentration.^a Islamabad, Pakistan.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers/plant	Straw yield (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)	K concentration (mg/g)	
					Straw	Grain
Control	121.3 b	6.4 c	46.1 c	20.2 c	10.90 a	6.76 b
166 kg K/ha	124.0 b	13.3 b	49.9 bc	21.5 c	11.81 a	13.88 a
0.7% K ₂ SO ₄	132.3 a	16.0 a	61.7 a	29.5 a	13.10 a	17.03 a
166 kg K/ha +0.7% K ₂ SO ₄	126.0 ab	12.7 b	55.4 b	25.6 b	13.90 a	13.39 a
LSD (0.05)	7	2.5	11.1	3.5	4.4	

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

transplanting resulted in significantly taller plants, more of productive tillers per plant, and higher straw and grain yield. K concentration in straw was not significantly affected by the treatments, but K application method affected K

concentration in rice grain. When 166 kg K/ha was applied with root dipping, plant height, productive tillers, and straw and grain yield were slightly lower. □

Breaking dormancy in *Sesbania rostrata*

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In an attempt to multiply seeds of *S. rostrata*, we planted on 19 Jun 1986 and harvested mature pods on 3 Nov 1986. In Mar 1987, practically no germination of seeds occurred, indicating the existence of dormancy. Attempts were made to break dormancy. Fifty seeds per treatment were arranged on soaked germination paper and kept in a germinator (25 °C). Germination was recorded daily to 7 d after treatment.

Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid

Germination of seeds of *Sesbania rostrata* as affected by various treatments. Dharwad, India, 1986.

Treatment	Germination (%)
Control	0
Hot water (60 °C for 5 min)	4
Gibberellic acid (GA ₃ 0.1%)	8
Sand scarification	8
Overnight soaking in water	12
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 20 min	28
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 25 min	44
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 30 min	88
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 35 min	88
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 40 min	96

was most effective in breaking dormancy (see table). However, there was considerable variation in

germination with time of treatment. Germination increased from 28% with 20 min to 96% with 40 min. □

Influence of paclobutrazol on rice seedling growth

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Rice Bai You Zhan No. 33 seedling growth was influenced by a soil drench of paclobutrazol granules at the one-leaf stage. Treated seedlings had faster leaf growth, shorter and stronger seedlings, higher tiller numbers, richer chlorophyll content, stronger rooting ability, and somewhat greater chilling resistance (see table). □